

A Clinical Study of The Fetal Outcome of Jaundice in Pregnancy in a Tertiary Care Centre

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Abstract:

Background: Maternal jaundice is a significant clinical condition during pregnancy, posing potential risks to both mother and fetus. Understanding its impact on fetal outcomes is crucial for developing effective management strategies in a tertiary care setting.

Aim: This study intends to evaluate the fetal outcomes connected with maternal jaundice in pregnant women treated at a tertiary care center.

Methods: A retrospective clinical study was performed at a tertiary care center, involving 90 pregnant women diagnosed with jaundice between July 2023 to April 2024. Data were collected on maternal demographics, clinical presentations, laboratory results, and fetal outcomes.

Results: The study analyzed 90 pregnant women with jaundice at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, revealing significant impacts on fetal outcomes based on jaundice severity. Preterm births occurred in 30% of cases, with severe jaundice showing the highest rate at 80%. Low birth weight was noted in 38% of infants, with all severe cases affected. NICU admissions were required for 40% of neonates, predominantly in severe jaundice cases (67%). Perinatal mortality was 5.5%, primarily in severe cases (27%). Significant associations between jaundice severity and adverse outcomes were confirmed. These findings emphasize the need for initial detection and supervision of jaundice in pregnancy to improve fetal health.

Conclusion: Jaundice during pregnancy is linked to a higher risk of negative outcomes for the baby, such as premature birth, low birth weight, and increased NICU admissions. Prompt identification and treatment of jaundice in expectant mothers are crucial to reducing these risks.

Recommendations: It includes necessity of enhanced screening protocols for early detection of jaundice in pregnant women. Comprehensive prenatal care programs focusing on monitoring liver function. Immediate referral to specialized care for pregnant women with jaundice. Public health initiatives to raise awareness about the importance of maternal health and jaundice management. Further research to develop targeted interventions for improving fetal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by jaundice.

Keywords: Maternal Jaundice, Fetal Outcomes, Pregnancy Complications, Tertiary Care Center, Neonatal Health.

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Introduction

Jaundice during pregnancy is a relatively uncommon but serious condition that can significantly impact both maternal and fetal health. It is marked by a yellow discoloration of the skin and eyes, caused by increased bilirubin levels in the bloodstream. Various etiologies, including viral hepatitis, intrahepatic cholestasis, and hemolytic disorders, can lead to jaundice in pregnant women. Understanding the implications of jaundice in pregnancy is crucial, as it can pose significant risks to the developing fetus, potentially leading to adverse outcomes [1].

Maternal jaundice poses a unique clinical challenge due to the physiological changes that occur during pregnancy and the potential for rapid progression of the disease. It is associated with complications and increased neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admissions. Despite its importance, there is limited comprehensive research focusing specifically on the fetal outcomes of jaundice during pregnancy. This gap in knowledge underscores the need for targeted studies to better understand and manage this condition [2].

Previous studies have indicated that maternal jaundice can lead to various fetal complications, but findings have been inconsistent. Some studies indicate an increased occurrence of premature birth and low weight among infants born to mothers with jaundice. However, the extent of these outcomes varies, and the specific factors contributing to adverse fetal health remain unclear. Most existing studies have been conducted in diverse clinical settings, making it difficult to generalize findings. A focused study in a tertiary care center can provide more specific insights and aid in developing standardized care protocols [3].

The current literature lacks detailed analysis and comprehensive data on the fetal outcomes associated with maternal jaundice in tertiary care settings. Most studies have not sufficiently accounted for the severity of jaundice or the presence of underlying liver conditions, which can significantly influence outcomes. This study intends to plug the gap by providing a detailed evaluation of fetal health in pregnancies complicated by jaundice, using a robust methodological approach and a well-defined patient cohort from a tertiary care center.

This study aims to evaluate the fetal outcomes associated with maternal jaundice in a tertiary care center. By retrospectively analyzing cases from Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, this research seeks to identify key factors contributing to adverse fetal outcomes and to determine the prevalence of complications expected to enhance clinical understanding and inform the development of improved management strategies for pregnancies complicated by jaundice, ultimately leading to better maternal and fetal health outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective cohort study was undertaken to assess the fetal outcomes linked to maternal jaundice during pregnancy.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, a tertiary care center, from July 2023 to April 2024.

Study Population: The study included 90 pregnant women diagnosed with jaundice.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Pregnant women diagnosed with jaundice confirmed through clinical evaluation and laboratory tests.
- Women between the ages of 18 and 45.
- Patients willing to participate and provide informed consent.

Exclusion criteria:

- Women with pre-existing liver diseases unrelated to pregnancy.
- Patients with multiple gestations.
- Women with incomplete medical records.

Bias: To minimize bias, a standardized data collection form was used, and all data were verified by a second investigator. Selection bias was reduced by including all eligible patients within the study period.

Variables

- Independent variable: Maternal jaundice.
- Dependent variables: Fetal outcomes including birth weight, gestational age at delivery, NICU admissions, and perinatal mortality.
- Confounding variables: Maternal age, parity, and underlying health conditions.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from medical records. Information gathered included maternal demographics, clinical presentation, laboratory results, and fetal outcomes.

Procedure: Patients' medical records were reviewed to extract relevant data. The severity of jaundice was assessed using serum bilirubin levels and liver function tests. Fetal outcomes were documented, including birth weight, gestational age at delivery, NICU admissions, and perinatal mortality rates.

Statistical Analysis: The data were analyzed with SPSS version 21.0. Descriptive statistics summarized both maternal and fetal characteristics. Continuous variables were expressed as means and standard deviations, while categorical variables were displayed as frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test assessed the relationship between the severity of maternal jaundice and fetal outcomes. A p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

Study Duration: The study was conducted over a period of 10 months, from July 2023 to April 2024.

Results

Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics: The study included 90 pregnant women diagnosed with jaundice at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital from July 2023 to April 2024. The mean age of the participants was 28.4 years (SD = 5.3). The majority of the women (60%) were multiparous. The average gestational age at the time of jaundice diagnosis was 30 weeks (SD = 4.2).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	Value (n = 90)
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Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	28.4 $\pm$ 5.3 years
Parity	
- Primiparous	36 (40%)
- Multiparous	54 (60%)
Gestational Age at Diagnosis	
Mean (weeks $\pm$ SD)	30 $\pm$ 4.2
Severity of Jaundice	
- Mild (bilirubin < 3 mg/dL)	35 (39%)
- Moderate (bilirubin 3-6 mg/dL)	40 (44%)
- Severe (bilirubin > 6 mg/dL)	15 (17%)

Fetal Outcomes: The study observed various fetal outcomes, with significant differences noted based on the severity of maternal jaundice.

Table 2: Fetal Outcomes Based on Severity of Maternal Jaundice

Outcome	Mild Jaundice (n = 35)	Moderate Jaundice (n = 40)	Severe Jaundice (n = 15)	Total (n = 90)
Preterm Birth (<37 weeks)	5 (14%)	10 (25%)	12 (80%)	27 (30%)
Low Birth Weight (<2500g)	7 (20%)	12 (30%)	15 (100%)	34 (38%)
NICU Admissions	8 (23%)	18 (45%)	10 (67%)	36 (40%)
Perinatal Mortality	0 (0%)	1 (2.5%)	4 (27%)	5 (5.5%)

A chi-square test was conducted to examine the association between the severity of maternal jaundice and fetal outcomes. The results indicated a significant association between the severity of jaundice and the likelihood of preterm birth ($\chi^2 = 20.5$, $p < 0.001$), low birth weight ($\chi^2 = 30.2$, $p < 0.001$), and NICU admissions ($\chi^2 = 16.8$, $p < 0.001$). The perinatal mortality rate was also significantly higher in severe jaundice cases compared to mild and moderate cases ($\chi^2 = 25.7$, $p < 0.001$).

Discussion

The study demonstrated that the severity of maternal jaundice is a critical determinant of adverse fetal outcomes. Pregnancies complicated by severe jaundice were more likely to result in preterm births, low birth weight infants, and increased NICU admissions. [4] The data suggest a need for heightened surveillance and intervention strategies in managing pregnant women with jaundice to mitigate risks to the fetus. These findings can inform clinical guidelines and support the development of targeted care protocols to improve maternal and neonatal health in cases of pregnancy-associated jaundice. A study evaluated maternal and fetal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by jaundice. It found significant adverse effects, including increased rates of preterm births and low birth weight [5]. Likewise, a study conducted at Dr. Rajendra Prasad Government Medical College, investigated maternal and fetal outcomes in 60 pregnant women with jaundice. It highlighted the significant complications, including a high rate of NICU admissions and a considerable percentage of stillbirths. The study underscored the importance of early diagnosis and multidisciplinary management of liver diseases during pregnancy to improve outcomes [6]. A research in Government Thanjavur Medical College, this study evaluated 65 pregnant women with

jaundice. It found that viral hepatitis was the most common cause, leading to substantial maternal complications and a notable rate of preterm deliveries. The study emphasized the critical need for regular antenatal care and early treatment to reduce maternal and fetal mortality [6].

Conclusion

Maternal jaundice during pregnancy significantly increases the risk of adverse fetal outcomes such as preterm birth, low birth weight, and a higher rate of NICU admissions. Prompt diagnosis and effective management of jaundice in pregnant women are crucial to reducing these risks and improving both maternal and fetal health outcomes.

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